

Decentralized Edge Learning: A Comparative Study of Distillation Strategies and Dissimilarity Measures

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Abstract

Decentralized learning is emerging as a scalable and privacy-preserving alternative to centralized machine learning, particularly in distributed systems where data cannot be centrally shared among multiple nodes or clients. While Federated Learning is widely adopted in this context, Knowledge Distillation (KD) is emerging as a flexible and scalable alternative where model output is used to share knowledge among distributed clients. However, existing studies often overlook the efficiency and effectiveness of various knowledge transfer strategies in KD, especially in decentralized environments where data is non-IID. This study provides key insights by examining the impact of network topology and distillation strategies in KD-based decentralized learning approaches. Our evaluation spans several dissimilarity measures, including Cross-Entropy, Kullback-Leibler divergence, Triangular Divergence, Jensen-Shannon divergence, Structural Entropic Distance, and Multi-way SED, assessed under both pairwise and holistic distillation schemes. In the pairwise approach, distillation is performed by summing the client-wise dissimilarities between a client's output and each neighbor's prediction individually, while the holistic approach computes dissimilarity with respect to the average of the output predictions received from neighboring clients.

We also analyze performance across client connectivity levels to explore the trade-off between convergence speed and model accuracy. The results indicate that the holistic distillation approach, which averages client predictions, outperforms the sum of pairwise distillation, especially when employing alternative measures like TD, SED, and JS. These measures offer improved performance over conventional metrics such as CE and KL divergence.

Keywords: Knowledge Distillation, Decentralized Learning, Information dissimilarity measure

1. Introduction

For many years, conventional cloud computing has been the cornerstone of large-scale data processing, offering centralized systems for storing and processing vast amounts of information [1]. However, as data generation is continuously increasing across various domains, an exclusive reliance on cloud-based processing has become increasingly inefficient. Moreover, the rapid expansion of the Internet of Things (IoT) [2, 3, 4] has made this problem even more challenging, resulting in a significant increase in both the amount and variety of data. This growth spans multiple sectors, including smart cities [5, 6], industrial automation [7, 8], environmental monitoring [9, 10], healthcare [11, 12], and many others. In the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Edge AI [13] has emerged as a viable alternative to traditional cloud-based processing, enabling AI applications to leverage an extensive and distributed data landscape more efficiently. By utilizing low-power computing devices at the network's edge, Edge AI minimizes reliance on centralized cloud infrastructure, thereby improving efficiency, reducing energy consumption, and lowering operational costs [14]. One of the most studied architectures for AI model training in Edge AI is Federated Learning (FL), which enables collaborative model training without requiring raw data to be centralized [15].

Another approach to distributed AI model training in Edge

AI is the distillation-based learning technique, which has emerged as a promising technique for decentralized model training. This approach utilizes *Knowledge Distillation* (KD) [16, 17, 18, 19], which follows the teacher-student paradigm, to facilitate efficient knowledge transfer. Decentralized KD leverages model outputs or intermediate representations to foster collaborative learning among distributed clients. Figure 1 illustrates a KD-based distributed learning framework where clients enhance their learning processes by sharing knowledge directly. Within this decentralized system, each client acts as both a learner (student) and a source of knowledge (teacher), fostering mutual improvement. In distillation-based decentralized learning, the primary information exchange occurs through the *distillation loss*, which is designed to ensure that each learning client aligns its output with those of its neighbors, enabling collaborative learning across the network. This distillation loss minimizes the difference between the “soft” predictions of intermediate model outputs of one client and those of all other connected clients. Usually, the distillation loss is combined with a *fully-supervised loss*, which is typically implemented using cross-entropy (CE) with “hard” targets derived from the ground-truth labels of the input samples [20].

A key advantage of the distillation paradigm is its flexibility, enabling clients to either benefit from both supervised learning and collaborative knowledge transfer, or to rely solely on the

Figure 1: A decentralized learning architecture based on KD comprising K clients, where knowledge transfer is effectively achieved through the distillation of model output representations.

distillation loss and shared knowledge within the network, thus eliminating the need for labeled data [21].

The traditional teacher-student KD framework enables the transfer of knowledge through both model predictions and intermediate model representations. This concept also applies in a distributed setting, where each client learns from a group of peers. In the case of distillation via model predictions [22], this knowledge transfer can be achieved by aggregating pairwise distillation across clients, each acting as a source of knowledge. For instance, Zhmoginov et al. [23] employed a pairwise distillation approach across clients using a small, shared i.i.d. subset of the overall dataset, ensuring that each client was exposed to all classes during the distillation process. However, this assumption is often unrealistic in practice, as such shared data is frequently unavailable due to privacy or data isolation constraints. In [24], we investigated the performance of distillation averaging among clients, comparing it to the conventional sum of pairwise distillation methods, and found promising results in enhancing knowledge transfer efficiency. Moreover, in contrast to most studies that adopt CE [25, 26] as the sole information dissimilarity measure for distillation, our previous work [24] has started exploring additional information dissimilarity measures, including Kullback-Leibler (KL) Divergence [27, 28], Triangular Divergence (TD), Structural Entropic Distance (SED), and Jensen-Shannon (JS) Divergence [29, 30]. However, those preliminary findings offered limited insight into the underlying factors and implications of the investigated dissimilarity measures, as the evaluation was conducted with a restricted number of nodes, leaving room for more comprehensive analysis.

This paper expands upon our earlier findings by conduct-

ing a thorough empirical study that delves into the dynamics of distillation-based learning for decentralized clients, with a focus on an iterative training approach encompassing a wide range of dissimilarity metrics and varying network topologies, to evaluate the effectiveness of different distillation strategies. Our key contributions include:

- We systematically evaluate the impact of different dissimilarity measures on the convergence speed of knowledge distillation in a fully decentralized network topology. Specifically, we quantify the number of communication iterations required for each measure to achieve the best performance under varying client connectivity.
- We provide a comparative analysis of the sum of pairwise distillation versus a holistic method that averages client predictions for distillation. Our analysis examines their impact on convergence speed and accuracy in the fully decentralized network, highlighting the effectiveness of direct peer interactions versus aggregated knowledge transfer.

Overall, in our experiments, we investigate the dynamics of decentralized distillation-based learning within a randomly structured network of interconnected clients. Specifically, we assess the performance of various dissimilarity measures by varying client degrees while employing a ResNet model with dual classification heads that iteratively perform knowledge distillation over multiple communication rounds. To evaluate the effectiveness of different dissimilarity measures in the decentralized framework, we consider two key scenarios: (a) integrating both supervised and distillation losses and (b) relying solely on the distillation loss.

This study offers a comprehensive analysis of the impact of various training strategies on convergence dynamics and overall model performance. The findings indicate that, in most instances, the holistic approach yields superior performance, particularly with respect to convergence speed over iterations. Furthermore, it effectively reduces variance in accuracy across all clients, providing a more balanced trade-off between effectiveness and efficiency. These insights highlight the potential of holistic strategies in enhancing model robustness and reliability, rendering them a promising option for real-world applications.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides background and related works on decentralized deep learning, knowledge distillation, and the dissimilarity measures used. Section 3 details the fully decentralized learning model discussed in this study. Section 4 presents our experimental evaluation. Finally, Section 5 provides the conclusions.

Table 1 summarizes the notations used throughout the paper.

2. Background and Related works

In this section, we provide background information on information dissimilarity measures employed in this work. Moreover, we outline basic information about Decentralized Deep Learning, followed by a discussion on KD in its general formulation.

2.1. Information Dissimilarity Measures and Statistical Divergences

Information distance quantifies the dissimilarity between two sources of information [31], such as finite objects based on the computational resources required to transform one into the other [32], and is closely related to statistical divergences, which measure dissimilarity between probability distributions. For instance, certain information distances, like SED, can compare probabilities, while statistical divergences can be viewed as information distances when the information sources are probability distributions. In the following, we provide formal definitions of the divergence functions and information distances used in this paper¹.

Kullback-Leibler Divergence. The KL divergence quantifies the information loss when one probability distribution, $\mathbf{q} = [q_1, \dots, q_n]$, is used to approximate another, $\mathbf{p} = [p_1, \dots, p_n]$. It is defined as:

$$KL(\mathbf{q} : \mathbf{p}) = \sum_{i=1}^n q_i \log \frac{q_i}{p_i} \quad (1)$$

Jensen-Shannon Divergence. The Jensen-Shannon (JS) divergence is a symmetrized and smoothed variant of the KL divergence. It represents the total KL divergence relative to the mean distribution $\frac{\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p}}{2}$ [34]. In this paper, we adopt the following definition:

¹Please note that as in [33] we use the delimiter ‘:’ as argument separator of non-symmetric divergence instead of the double bar notation ‘||’ used in information theory.

$$JS(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \frac{1}{2} KL\left(\mathbf{q} : \frac{\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p}}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{2} KL\left(\mathbf{p} : \frac{\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p}}{2}\right) \quad (2)$$

Structural Entropic Distance. The SED [35] is an information-theoretic measure that compares the Shannon entropy H of two probability vectors to that of their arithmetic mean. The Shannon entropy, defined as $H(\mathbf{p}) = -\sum_{i=1}^n p_i \ln p_i$, quantifies the information required to describe the probability vector \mathbf{p} [36]. For two probability vectors \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{q} , SED is computed as the ratio of the entropy of their mean vector to the geometric mean of the entropies of the individual vectors:

$$SED(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \frac{C\left(\frac{\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p}}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{C(\mathbf{q})C(\mathbf{p})}} - 1, \quad (3)$$

where $C(\mathbf{x}) = b^{-\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \log_b x_i}$ is referred to as the *complexity* (or perplexity). The expression in Eq. (3) produces a value in the range $[0, 1]$, where 0 indicates the two input vectors are identical, and 1 indicates they are orthogonal.

Eq. (3) can be generalized to multiple arguments such that:

$$MSED(\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_m) = \frac{1}{m-1} \left(\frac{C\left(\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \mathbf{p}_i\right)}{\sqrt[m]{\prod_{i=1}^m C(\mathbf{p}_i)}} - 1 \right) \quad (4)$$

referred to as Multi-way SED (or MSED), where Eq. (4) remains a ratio of the complexity of a centroid to the geometric mean of the complexities of its neighboring vectors. The function exhibits the following properties: it yields 0 when all vectors are identical, 1 when all vectors are different, and values between these extremes for all other inputs.

Triangular Divergence. The Triangular Divergence (TD)² or Triangular Discrimination [38], is defined as: $TD(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(q_i - p_i)^2}{q_i + p_i}$. Since its range is $[0, 2]$, we use the scaled version in our work:

$$TD(\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(q_i - p_i)^2}{q_i + p_i} = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{2q_i p_i}{q_i + p_i} \quad (5)$$

where the optimized form on the right-hand side follows from the identity $(q_i - p_i)^2 = (q_i + p_i)^2 - 4q_i p_i$ and the normalization $\sum_{i=1}^n p_i = \sum_{i=1}^n q_i = 1$.

Cross Entropy. Cross Entropy (CE) is a commonly used divergence measure in machine learning to quantify the difference between two probability distributions. It is defined as:

$$CE(\mathbf{q} : \mathbf{p}) = -\sum_{i=1}^n q_i \log p_i \quad (6)$$

It is important to mention that in machine learning, as demonstrated in [33], measures like CE, KL divergence, JS di-

²Its square root is a metric known as *Triangular Distance*, *Vincze-Le Cam distance*, and the symmetric *chi-squared distance* [37]

Table 1: Summary of notation used

Notation	Description
$\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}_i$	Probability vectors
n	Dimension of probability vectors/ number of classes
$H(\mathbf{p})$	Shannon entropy
$C(\mathbf{p})$	Complexity (perplexity) of a probability vector
$CE(\mathbf{p} : \mathbf{q})$	Cross-entropy divergence
$JS(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})$	Jensen-Shannon Divergence
$KL(\mathbf{p} : \mathbf{q})$	Kullback-Leibler Divergence
$TD(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})$	Triangular Divergence
$SED(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})$	Structural Entropic Distance
$MSED(\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_m)$	Multi-way Structural Entropic Distance
x	Generic input sample
τ	Temperature parameter used in the softmax function
$\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}(x)$	Logit vector (i.e., raw model outputs before applying softmax)
$\mathbf{p}(x, \tau)$	Soft probability distributions obtained by applying softmax with temperature τ to the logits $\mathbf{z}(x)$
$\mathbf{p}(x), \mathbf{p}(x, 1)$	Hard probability distributions obtained by applying softmax with temperature $\tau = 1$
$\mathbf{p}_S(x, \tau), \mathbf{p}_T(x, \tau)$	In a KD setting, denote the softened probability distributions produced by the student and teacher networks, respectively
$\mathbf{p}_S(x, 1)$	In a KD setting, denote the hard probability distributions produced by the student networks
$(\mathcal{G}, \varepsilon)$	Graph-based network of clients
$\mathcal{G} = \{C^k \mid k \in K\}$	Set of clients (nodes) in the graph
ε	Set of edges connecting the clients
N	Node degree
K	Total number of clients
k	Index identifying a client in the network (referred to as the <i>current</i> client)
Φ^k	Set of indices of clients directly connected to C^k (i.e., its <i>neighbors</i>)
$\phi \in \Phi^k$	Index identifying a neighbor of the current client k
$D^k = (X^k, Y^k)$	Local labeled dataset on client k , where X^k is the set of input data and Y^k are the corresponding labels
$(x, y) \in D^k$	Data sample x and the corresponding label y
$\mathcal{M}_{h_1}^k, \mathcal{M}_{h_2}^k$	First-head and second-head models of client k
t	Index of the current training iteration
t_{\max}	Maximum number of training iterations
$\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k,t}$	Second-head model of client k at iteration t
\mathbf{w}_2	Parameters of the second-head model $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k,t}$
$\mathcal{L}^k, \mathcal{L}_{\text{stu}}^k, \mathcal{L}_{\text{KD}}^k$	Total loss, supervised student loss, and distillation loss for client k
$\mathbf{p}^{k,t}(\mathbf{w}_2; x)$	Soft prediction of client k at iteration t ; the dependence on \mathbf{w}_2 is made explicit to emphasize its role in the gradient computation during optimization.
$\mathbf{p}^{k,t-1}(x)$	Soft prediction of client k at previous iteration
$\mathbf{p}^{\phi,t-1}(x)$	Soft prediction of neighbor client ϕ at previous iteration
$\mathbf{p}_{\text{avg}}^{k,t-1}(x)$	Average soft prediction of client k and its neighbors at iteration $t-1$
$f(\cdot, \cdot)$	Divergence function used for distillation (e.g., CE, KL, JS, SED, TD)
γ	Skewness parameter controlling the degree of non-iid data distribution across clients

vergence, and Triangular Divergence (TD) exhibit strong correlations in certain spaces. Specifically, when \mathbf{q} is fixed, the perfect correlation between cross-entropy and KL divergence arises from the algebraic relationship $KL(\mathbf{q} : \mathbf{p}) = CE(\mathbf{q} : \mathbf{p}) - H(\mathbf{q})$ [33]. Additionally, JS divergence nearly perfectly correlates with TD in high-dimensional spaces [38], and CE and TD are strongly correlated when the probabilities are obtained from the softmax function (Eq. (7)) with a high temperature. Notably, TD is computationally less expensive than CE, so if the correlation is sufficiently strong, the former may serve as a suitable substitute.

2.2. Decentralized Deep Learning

Decentralized deep learning (DDL) [39] has facilitated the emergence of Edge AI, a paradigm that integrates Edge Computing and artificial intelligence to generate intelligent insights independently of centralized computational resources [40, 41]. Initially, DDL was conceptualized to facilitate the training of large-scale neural networks, encompassing billions of parameters, distributed across thousands of CPU cores [42]. Unlike traditional centralized training frameworks, DDL employs edge computing to process sensitive client data locally on user devices, thereby addressing privacy concerns while simultaneously reducing communication overhead and data management complexities [43].

In decentralized systems, various approaches have been explored for sharing useful information (i.e., knowledge) to enhance performance [44]. Federated learning [15, 45] has been extensively studied in the literature. Furthermore, methods based on KD have recently garnered increasing attention in the field. In the following, we present knowledge distillation as an emerging approach for facilitating information exchange among participating clients in decentralized systems.

2.2.1. Knowledge Distillation

KD was originally proposed as a technique for transferring knowledge from large, pre-trained teacher networks to smaller, student networks. This process involves approximating the soft outputs or intermediate representations of the teacher to create a more compact and efficient model [46].

Specifically, for any input x , the teacher network produces a vector of logits $\mathbf{z}(x) = [z_1(x), \dots, z_n(x)]$, which is typically transformed into a probability vector $\mathbf{p}(x) = [p_1(x), \dots, p_n(x)]$ using the softmax function: $p_i(x) = \frac{e^{z_i(x)}}{\sum_{j=1}^n e^{z_j(x)}}$. For distillation, a modified softmax with a temperature parameter is commonly used to produce soft targets. These soft targets are intended to enhance the informativeness of the probability distribution by smoothing the sharp peaks of the classic softmax output. The adjusted softmax is expressed as:

$$p_i(x, \tau) = \frac{e^{z_i(x)/\tau}}{\sum_{j=1}^n e^{z_j(x)/\tau}}, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\} \quad (7)$$

where τ is the temperature hyperparameter. This modified version of the softmax allows the student network to learn from the teacher's softened predictions, transferring the underlying

knowledge in a more informative and robust manner. To assess the similarity between the outputs of the teacher and student networks, the CE loss is frequently used and formulated as the distillation loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{KD} = CE(\mathbf{p}_T(x, \tau) : \mathbf{p}_S(x, \tau)) \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_S(x, \tau)$ and $\mathbf{p}_T(x, \tau)$ represent the softened probability distributions generated by the student and the teacher networks, respectively.

Furthermore, for classification tasks, the cross-entropy loss is employed as an additional component of the overall objective function to evaluate the discrepancy between the student network's predictions and the ground truth labels:

$$\mathcal{L}_{stu} = CE(\mathbf{y} : \mathbf{p}_S(x, 1)) \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{y} represents the ground truth, and $\mathbf{p}_S(x, 1)$ is the "hard" probability distributions (i.e., using $\tau = 1$) generated by the student.

Thus, the total loss function for the student network can be expressed as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{stu} + (1 - \alpha) \mathcal{L}_{KD} \quad (10)$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is a hyperparameter.

In DDL, KD facilitates information exchange not only between models where the teacher is more complex than the student but also between models with the same or different architectures. For instance, Molo et al. [24] utilized models with identical architectures to train DDL models. Similarly, Shi et al. [44] examined the use of KD in decentralized manufacturing systems. Their study focused on the effectiveness of KD among units with identical model architectures, where some units had access to larger and more diverse local datasets than others. Zhmoginov et al. [23] explored information exchange using models with varying architectures. Their findings highlight that smaller models benefit most during the learning phase when the network includes a mix of larger and comparable architectures across devices. Yin et al. [47] investigated KD for decentralized devices using multi-modal data. They employed dual-head ResNet-18 models on all devices, featuring a shared classifier in one head and modality-specific classifiers in the other.

As KD continues to evolve, bridging the gap between advanced DDL AI models and practical deployment constraints remains essential, highlighting the need to explore more effective and efficient knowledge transfer methods [48]. To the best of our knowledge, state-of-the-art applications have not employed alternative information distance metrics beyond cross-entropy and KL divergence for knowledge transfer between models. In this work, we analyze the dynamics of DDL, focusing on alternative information dissimilarity measures.

3. Methodology

In this section, we detail the KD-based decentralized learning framework, including the learning procedure and the formulation of the distillation loss strategy for analyzing system dynamics.

We model the decentralized network as an undirected graph $(\mathcal{G}, \varepsilon)$, where $\mathcal{G} = \{C^k \mid k \in K\}$ represents the set of clients C^k , indexed by $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, and ε denotes the edges connecting clients. For each client C^k , we define Φ^k , the set of its directly connected neighbors. We assume that clients can communicate only with their neighbors.

Each client C^k holds a local dataset $D^k = (X^k, Y^k)$, where $X^k = \{x_i\}$ and $Y^k = \{y_i\}$ are the input data and ground-truth labels, respectively. Each client also owns a dual-head neural network model consisting of a shared backbone and two classification heads with identical architecture. We denote the first and second heads connected to the shared backbone as $\mathcal{M}_{h_1}^k$ and $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^k$, respectively.³

Decentralized Learning via Iterative Knowledge Distillation.

In our KD-based decentralized learning framework, each client initially trains its first-head model in a supervised manner using its own local annotated dataset. Then, the second-head model is trained through knowledge transfer from its neighboring clients. Specifically, all second-head models are initialized with the pre-trained first-head model and then fine-tuned using soft predictions obtained from both the client's own second-head and those of its neighbors. This process enables each client to benefit from its neighbors' knowledge, effectively treating them as a collective teacher in a teacher-student paradigm. To facilitate knowledge propagation from distant clients (potentially several hops away), this knowledge exchange occurs over a fixed number of synchronized iterations. We assume that iterations are synchronized, meaning each iteration begins only after the previous one completes. An illustration of this iterative knowledge distillation process is shown in Figure 2, highlighting the dual-head architecture and the information exchange across clients during iterative training.

The previously described learning approach can be formalized as follows. Each client maintains a dual-head model, where the model with the first head, $\mathcal{M}_{h_1}^k$, is trained in a fully supervised manner using the ground truth labels Y^k , while the model with the second head, $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^k$, is fine-tuned or refined through knowledge distillation from the neighboring clients in Φ^k .

At the initial iteration ($t = 0$), each client C^k trains its first-head model $\mathcal{M}_{h_1}^k$ on its local dataset D^k . The resulting weights are then used to initialize the second-head model $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^k$, which is subsequently shared with the client's neighbors. Starting from the next iteration ($t > 0$), each client receives the second-head models from its neighbors $\{\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{\phi, t-1}, \phi \in \Phi^k\}$ and uses them, along with its own previous second-head model $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k, t-1}$ to further fine-tune the new second-head model $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k, t}$ through knowledge distillation. Importantly, $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k, t}$ is always initialized from

³The dual-head design is adopted for convenience, as it allows us to isolate the impact of distillation from standard supervised learning within a single model. Specifically, the first head serves as a supervised-only baseline, while the second head incorporates the distillation loss. This design simplifies the analysis but is not a requirement: our approach can also be implemented using a single-head model, depending on the deployment scenario.

the previous iteration's weights $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k, t-1}$, and this process is repeated until a maximum number of iterations t_{max} is reached.⁴

The parameters \mathbf{w}_2 of the current second-head model $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k, t}$ are specifically trained by minimizing the following local total loss

$$\mathcal{L}^k = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{stu}^k + (1 - \alpha) \mathcal{L}_{KD}^k, \quad (11)$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ controls the balance between the supervised loss, \mathcal{L}_{stu}^k , and the distillation loss, \mathcal{L}_{KD}^k . In the extreme case where $\alpha = 0$, the learning is entirely based on distillation, and when $\alpha = 1$, only the local ground-truth labels are used for training using the supervised student loss.

For the student loss, we employ the standard cross-entropy loss,

$$\mathcal{L}_{stu}^k(\mathbf{w}_2; D^k) = \mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim D^k} \mathcal{L}_{CE}(\mathbf{w}_2; x, y), \quad (12)$$

which encourages the model to align its predictions with the ground-truth labels from the local dataset.⁵

The distillation loss \mathcal{L}_{KD}^k is instead designed to integrate knowledge from other clients' models by comparing the soft predictions across iterations and neighbors.

Computing the Knowledge Distillation Loss. To compute the distillation loss, we explore two distinct cases, each representing a different strategy for aggregating and comparing probability distributions across neighboring clients and previous iterations.

Specifically, let $\mathbf{p}^{k, t}(\mathbf{w}_2; x)$ be the output probability distribution generated by the current second-head model $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k, t}$ on input x , and $\mathbf{p}^{\phi, t-1}(x)$ be the output probability distribution from a direct neighbor $\phi \in \Phi^k$ using its second-head model at the previous iteration $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{\phi, t-1}$ on the same input x . Let $\mathbf{p}^{k, t-1}(x)$ denote the output probability distribution from the client's own previous second-head model $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k, t-1}$. We consider two alternative formulations for the distillation loss, reflecting different strategies for aggregating the soft predictions received from neighbors and the client's own past model:

- **Case 1:** *Pairwise dissimilarity-based distillation*, where each current client minimizes the sum of pairwise divergences with each neighbor and with its own previous soft predictions:

$$\mathcal{L}_{KD}^k(\mathbf{w}_2; X^k) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim X^k} \left(f(\mathbf{p}^{k, t}(\mathbf{w}_2; x), \mathbf{p}^{k, t-1}(x)) + \sum_{\phi \in \Phi^k} f(\mathbf{p}^{k, t}(\mathbf{w}_2; x), \mathbf{p}^{\phi, t-1}(x)) \right) \quad (13)$$

- **Case 2:** *Holistic distillation*, where the target distribution is modeled as the average of the soft predictions from the

⁴Alternative stopping criteria could be employed, for example by monitoring accuracy improvements across clients. However, we leave the exploration of such strategies as future work.

⁵We use the notation $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{w}_2; x, y)$ to explicitly separate the model parameters \mathbf{w}_2 , which are optimized during training, from the data inputs (x, y) . This highlights the role of \mathbf{w}_2 in the gradient computation.

Figure 2: Illustration of our iterative KD-based decentralized training framework on a network with K clients. Each client is equipped with a dual-head neural network. Initially, the first head model is trained on the local dataset and then used to initialize the second head model, which is shared with the directly connected clients. In each training iteration, the second head is fine-tuned using a knowledge distillation approach, where the knowledge transfer relies on the soft predictions from the second heads of both the client itself and its neighbors, as obtained in the previous iteration.

client and its neighbors at the previous iteration:

$$\mathcal{L}_{KD}^k(\mathbf{w}_2; X^k) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim X^k} f(\mathbf{p}^{k,t}(\mathbf{w}_2; x), \mathbf{p}_{avg}^{k,t-1}(x)) \quad (14)$$

with

$$p_{avg}^{k,t-1}(x) = \frac{\mathbf{p}^{k,t-1}(x) + \sum_{\phi \in \Phi_k} \mathbf{p}^\phi(x)}{|\Phi_k| + 1} \quad (15)$$

The function f in both Eq 13 and 14 represents any divergence function, such as CE, KL, TD, SED, or JS introduced in Section 2.1.

As part of the holistic approach, we also evaluate the performance of the MSED divergence as the distillation metric. Unlike traditional pairwise divergence functions, MSED is a multivariate function that quantifies the overall alignment between multiple probability distributions. In this case, the comparison is not performed between the current model's prediction and the average of previous soft predictions. Instead, MSED is applied to the set composed of the current client's prediction $\mathbf{p}^k(\mathbf{w}_2, x)$, the predictions of its direct neighbors $\{\mathbf{p}^\phi(x)\}_{\phi \in \Phi_k}$, and the client's own prediction from the previous iteration $\mathbf{p}^{k,t-1}(x)$. In this case, the distillation loss $\mathcal{L}_{KD}^k(\mathbf{w}_2; X^k)$ is defined as:

$$\mathbb{E}_{x \sim X^k} \text{MSED} \left(\mathbf{p}^{k,t}(\mathbf{w}_2; x), \mathbf{p}^{k,t-1}(x), \{\mathbf{p}^\phi(x)\}_{\phi \in \Phi_k} \right) \quad (16)$$

This formulation allows the distillation process to simultaneously consider the collective knowledge from the neighborhood

and the temporal evolution of the local model.

In Algorithm 1, we summarize the proposed iterative distillation training procedure. This algorithm reflects our dual-head design, where the first-head model is specialized in the local task and trained solely with the fully supervised loss, while the second-head model incorporates the distillation loss to learn from peer models and generalize beyond the local data. The overarching goal of this design is to enable each client to benefit from knowledge available in the decentralized network, going beyond its own data distribution.

4. Experimental Evaluation

In this section, we present the results of our experimental analysis, which evaluates the performance of the proposed decentralized knowledge distillation framework using different divergence measures. The experimental setup is described in Section 4.1, while the results and their analysis are discussed in Section 4.2.

4.1. Experimental setup

To perform our evaluation, we designed an experimental setup that simulates a decentralized learning scenario with knowledge distillation. Our analysis was conducted on a randomly interconnected network of eight clients. The network's topology, specifically the node degree, significantly influences

Figure 3: The topologies used in the experiments. From left to right, every node increases its degree by two, going from the 3 of the left topology to the 7 (fully connected network) of the right. The added links are represented with different dot patterns for each degree value.

Algorithm 1: Iterative Decentralized Training with Knowledge Distillation

Data: (\mathcal{G}, ϵ) : Graph representing a network of K clients $\{C_1, \dots, C_K\}$
Local datasets $D^k = (X^k, Y^k)$, where X^k is the set of input data and Y^k are the corresponding labels
Result: Trained second-head models $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^k$ for all clients

```

// Initialization Phase
foreach client  $C^k$ ,  $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$  in parallel do
  /* Train first-head model on  $D^k$  */
   $\mathcal{M}_{h_1}^k \leftarrow \text{LocalModelTraining}(\mathcal{L}_{CE}^k(\mathbf{w}_1; D^k))$ 
  /* Initialize second-head with  $\mathcal{M}_{h_1}^k$  */
   $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k,0} \leftarrow \mathcal{M}_{h_1}^k$ 
end
for  $t = 1$  to  $t_{max}$  do
  // Communication Phase
  foreach client  $C^k$ ,  $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$  in parallel do
    Identify  $\Phi_k$  as the set of direct neighbors in  $\mathcal{G}$ 
    Share  $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k,t-1}$  with all  $\phi \in \Phi_k$ 
    Receive models  $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{\phi,t-1}$  from all  $\phi \in \Phi_k$ 
  end
  // Distillation and Local Model Update
  foreach client  $C^k$ ,  $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$  in parallel do
    /* Initialize current model with previous iteration */
     $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k,t} \leftarrow \mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k,t-1}$ 
    /* Compute distillation loss  $\mathcal{L}_{KD}^k$  using Eq.13, Eq.14, or 16 */
     $\mathcal{L}_{KD}^k(\mathbf{w}_2; X^k) = \text{ComputeDistillationLoss}(\mathbf{p}^k(\mathbf{w}_2; x), \{\mathbf{p}^\phi(x)\}_{\phi \in \Phi_k}, \mathbf{p}^{k,t-1}(x))$ 
    /* Compute student supervised loss  $\mathcal{L}_{stu}^k$  using Eq. 12 */
     $\mathcal{L}_{stu}^k(\mathbf{w}_2; D^k) = \text{ComputeStudentLoss}(\mathbf{p}^k(\mathbf{w}_2; x), y)$ 
    /* Train with total loss:  $\mathcal{L}^k = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{stu}^k + (1 - \alpha) \mathcal{L}_{KD}^k$  */
     $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k,t} \leftarrow \text{LocalModelTraining}(\mathcal{L}^k(\mathbf{w}_2; D^k))$ 
    Store  $\mathcal{M}_{h_2}^{k,t}$  for the next iteration
  end
end

```

the learning paradigm. As illustrated in Figure 3, we systematically varied the node degree (N), defined as the number of edges connected to a client, to assess the performance of various dissimilarity measures in the distillation process.

In our previous work [24], we observed that when clients follow an i.i.d. data distribution, the choice of divergence measure has a limited impact on performance. Therefore, in this study, we focus on a more challenging and realistic non-iid setting, where each client specializes in a subset of classes or data instances. Within this framework, we evaluated the effectiveness of six dissimilarity measures: CE, KL, SED, MSED, TD, and JS.

4.1.1. Dataset

For our experiments, we used the CIFAR-10 [49] and the Fashion-MNIST [50] datasets, both datasets composed of 10 classes with a total of 60,000 images for the training set. We distributed the training data in a non-iid manner across eight clients, reserving a separate set of 10,000 images for centralized testing. These information are summarized in Table 2

Table 2: Dataset Statistics

Dataset	Training-set	Test-set	Number of Classes
CIFAR-10	60,000	10,000	10
Fashion-MNIST	60,000	10,000	10

To create the non-i.i.d. partitioning of both datasets among clients, we adopt the approach proposed by Zhmoginov et al.[23]. Let $\{y_1, \dots, y_n\}$ denote the set of class labels in the dataset. Each client C^k is assigned a subset of these labels as its primary labels, while the remaining labels are treated as secondary. For each class label y_i , the corresponding samples are allocated across clients with a bias: samples are $(1 + \gamma)$ times more likely to be assigned to clients for which y_i is a primary label. The skewness parameter γ controls the strength of this non-i.i.d. effect. When $\gamma = 0$, the dataset is distributed uniformly (i.i.d.), and all classes are equally likely to appear on each client. As γ increases, samples of a given class become increasingly concentrated on clients for which the class is primary. In the extreme case $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, each class would be exclusively assigned to a subset of clients.

It is important to note that, while class labels may overlap across clients, we ensured that each client receives a disjoint set

Figure 4: Class distribution of training samples across clients for CIFAR-10 dataset. Each bar represents a client, and each segment within the bar indicates the number of samples from a specific class. The skewed allocation results in class imbalance and label overlap across clients, reflecting the non-i.i.d. nature of the data.

of data instances. Image files were moved (not copied) from the original dataset to client-specific folders, guaranteeing that no image appears on more than one client. This approach creates sample-wise exclusivity while preserving realistic label overlap, thereby simulating practical decentralized learning conditions.

In our experiments, we set $\gamma = 100$, as in [23], ensuring a high level of data heterogeneity across clients. To illustrate the resulting data distribution, Figure 4 shows the class distribution of training samples across clients using a stacked bar plot for the CIFAR-10 dataset. Each bar represents a client, with segments indicating the number of samples per class. This visualization highlights class imbalance and label overlap, reflecting the non-i.i.d. nature of the data induced by the skewness parameter γ .

Performance was evaluated using the full test set distribution of the specific dataset, which contains samples from all ten classes. For each client, we computed the accuracy of its local model and reported the average accuracy across all clients.

4.1.2. Implementation Details

Below, we provide the key implementation details of our experimental setup, including model architecture, training configuration, and deployment environment.

All models were based on ResNet18 [51], initialized with ImageNet pre-trained weights from PyTorch. Standard data augmentation approaches, as recommended in the PyTorch documentation⁶, were applied during training. We opted for a dual-head model primarily for implementation convenience, enabling a direct comparison between the performance of the head trained without distillation and the one trained using KD. However, our methodology can also be implemented with a single head. Both heads in the dual-head architecture used the

same number of parameters to facilitate the distillation procedure. The first head provides a reference point for model performance when trained without knowledge distillation. In contrast, the second head incorporates the distillation loss to learn from peer models and generalize beyond the local data. Unlike the approach proposed by Zhmoginov et al. [23], which uses multiple heads to preserve historical knowledge for distillation, we adopt a more parameter-efficient alternative. Since adding a head per iteration would significantly increase the model size over time, we maintain a fixed dual-head architecture in which the second head is iteratively updated throughout training.

Training was performed with a batch size of 128 and six workers. The SGD optimizer was used with an initial learning rate of 0.001, momentum of 0.9, and weight decay of 5×10^{-4} .

Distillation experiments were conducted with temperature values of $\tau = 1$ for the Holistic approach and $\tau = 10$ for the pairwise approach. The temperature was selected based on the best trade-off of the overall accuracy across all clients.

To understand our methodology’s general trend, we evaluated the impact of the weighting parameter α (from Eq.(10)) using values of $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 0.5$ on the CIFAR-10 dataset. This trend was then validated on the Fashion-MNIST dataset, utilizing $\alpha = 0.5$. In doing so, experimenting with these two α values enabled us to analyze both a pure distillation scenario, where client supervision relies solely on soft labels, and a hybrid scenario, which combines ground-truth labels with soft labels.

Our implementation utilized eight independent Docker containers, each corresponding to a client and storing model checkpoints in a shared folder. During the second-head model training, each client loaded the second-head models of its neighboring clients from this shared folder to compute the distillation loss. This setup was adopted for practical reasons, as it allows for a simplified and reproducible implementation of the decentralized training process without the need to simulate real-time inter-client communication. As future work, we plan to extend

⁶<https://pytorch.org/vision/main/models/generated/torchvision.models.resnet101.html>

this framework with a detailed analysis of communication costs and to explore its deployment on real edge devices in fully distributed settings.

The code to reproduce the experiments is available at https://github.com/joaquimbasa/Distributed_KD_Information_Dissimilarity.git under the branch `Distillation_Strategies_Decentralized_Edge_Learning`.

4.2. Results

To evaluate the performance of the implemented system, both efficiency and effectiveness are considered. Efficiency was assessed by comparing the convergence rates of the conventional sum of pairwise distillation and the holistic approach. Effectiveness was evaluated on both the overall accuracy achieved by the models and by analyzing how well each KD strategy reduced performance disparities across the network. The results reveal a trade-off between accuracy and convergence rate, aiding in the selection of appropriate methods and dissimilarity metrics for KD-based decentralized frameworks.

4.2.1. System Convergence rate

The following analysis examines the efficiency of decentralized learning as influenced by dissimilarity measures, KD formulations, and node degree.

Figure 5 and 6 show how quickly each method reaches its peak accuracy across different dissimilarity measures and node degrees, considering all eight clients for CIFAR-10 dataset. Specifically, we compared the conventional pairwise approach with the holistic approach, based on settings where $\alpha = 0$, wherein only the distillation loss is used, and $\alpha = 0.5$, wherein the loss combines the distillation and the student's supervised loss, as defined in Eq. 10. In our experiments, the iteration count is determined by analyzing the convergence behavior depending on the value of α . We perform 5 iterations for the values of $\alpha = 0$ and 10 iterations for $\alpha = 0.5$. The limited number of iterations for $\alpha = 0$ is motivated by the observed performance drop over iterations for both distillation strategies as shown in Figure 5, in contrast to the behavior at $\alpha = 0.5$, where the pairwise approach exhibited clear performance improvements over iterations.

Generally, the holistic approach demonstrates faster convergence than the pairwise method across most tested cases. However, a notable exception occurs when $\alpha = 0$ and the node degree is 3: in this specific scenario, both distillation strategies exhibit relatively similar convergence rates and achieve comparable overall accuracy at their best iteration (iteration 1 and 2). In contrast, for higher node degrees, dissimilarity measures such as TD, JS, and SED consistently converged rapidly (often within the first iteration) and also achieved higher peak accuracy compared to their respective counterparts in the pairwise approach. On the other hand, in the pairwise approach, CE and KL divergence primarily reached their best accuracy during the second iteration for node degrees 3 and 5, and impressively achieved peak accuracy within the first iteration for a node degree of 7. For $\alpha = 0.5$ (Figure 6), all dissimilarity measures exhibit faster convergence in the holistic approach, with the effect

becoming even more pronounced as the node degree increases. For instance, when the node degree is 7, all measures reach their peak accuracy within the first iteration. Moreover, the best-achieved accuracy is also consistently higher in the holistic case for the TD, JS and SED dissimilarity measures.

Finally, for reference, we also included the results for MSED in the holistic approach. Note that a corresponding pairwise version of MSED does not exist. Overall, MSED appears to be the least efficient option, consistently exhibiting slower convergence among the holistic approaches.

Beyond faster convergence, the holistic approach also demonstrates another efficiency advantage that becomes evident when comparing the KD loss formulations for the pairwise (Eq.(13)) and holistic (Eq.(14)) strategies. In the conventional formulation, where predictions from different clients are processed individually, each knowledge source requires a separate evaluation of the function f . This introduces a computational overhead proportional to the number of a client's neighbors, resulting in a complexity of $O(N)$ assuming a uniform node degree N across clients. In contrast, the holistic approach first averages the predictions from neighboring models before applying the function f , thereby reducing the number of divergence computations. While both approaches share the same asymptotic complexity $O(N)$ in terms of prediction gathering from neighboring clients, the holistic formulation significantly reduces the constant factor, as it requires only a single divergence evaluation. As a result, the averaging-based approach offers better scalability for large neighborhood sizes and is more suitable for computationally intensive scenarios. Moreover, this improves efficiency without compromising knowledge transfer effectiveness as discussed in more detail in the following subsection.

4.2.2. Average Accuracy and Variance Across Clients

The non-iid data distributions across clients in \mathcal{G} lead to performance variations after distillation. Therefore, comparing the average accuracy variance between the pairwise and holistic approaches is important to provide a comprehensive picture and highlight scenarios in which larger performance discrepancies among clients emerge. Tables Figure 5 and 6 also present the variance at each iteration for both pairwise and holistic strategies. The results show a significant reduction in variance with the holistic methods. This can be attributed to the fact that, unlike the pairwise strategy, which compares the model's prediction to each peer individually, potentially amplifying noise from non-i.i.d. predictions, the holistic approach averages the outputs from all peers into a single, smoothed target. This averaging not only reduces the variance in the distillation targets but also results in less noisy gradients during backpropagation, leading to more stable updates. As a result, the holistic method provides a more stable and reliable training signal, which helps the model learn more smoothly, especially in decentralized settings where client predictions can vary widely due to non-i.i.d. data.

In the low-connectivity scenario ($N = 3$) using the pairwise distillation approach with $\alpha = 0$ (Figure 5a), we observed that CE and KL divergences slightly outperform the first-head

Table 3: *Pure distillation setting ($\alpha = 0$), CIFAR-10 dataset.* Comparison of average accuracy (taken as the average accuracy per client per 5 seeds) for Holistic and Pairwise Distillation strategies across different node degrees ($N = 3, 5, 7$). The Std. Dev. values represent the variance across seeds. Bold values represent the highest accuracy within each node degree configuration, while underlined values indicate the second highest. The \pm columns indicate the standard deviation across seeds.

Function	Distillation Strategy	Node Degree 3		Node Degree 5		Node Degree 7	
		Accuracy	\pm Std. Dev.	Accuracy	\pm Std. Dev.	Accuracy	\pm Std. Dev.
CE	Holistic	57.81	0.77	57.16	4.03	59.97	1.91
	Pairwise	<u>60.43</u>	0.90	66.66	0.66	<u>70.09</u>	0.49
KL	Holistic	57.58	3.12	59.32	3.47	59.13	3.47
	Pairwise	60.64	0.55	<u>66.64</u>	0.62	70.10	0.54
TD	Holistic	59.48	1.09	64.94	0.94	67.60	0.72
	Pairwise	58.13	0.36	62.94	0.35	64.83	0.58
JS	Holistic	57.65	4.15	65.68	0.65	68.99	0.32
	Pairwise	58.63	1.85	60.77	0.50	60.10	1.09
SED	Holistic	58.05	3.27	64.53	0.52	68.46	0.64
	Pairwise	58.77	1.74	60.52	0.96	59.78	0.38
MSED	Holistic	59.63	3.61	62.99	0.81	65.07	1.04

Table 4: *Pure distillation setting ($\alpha = 0.5$), CIFAR-10 dataset.* Comparison of average accuracy (taken as the average accuracy per client per 5 seeds) for Holistic and Pairwise Distillation strategies across different node degrees ($N = 3, 5, 7$). The Std. Dev. values represent the variance across seeds. Bold values represent the highest accuracy within each node degree configuration, while underlined values indicate the second highest. The \pm columns indicate the standard deviation across seeds.

Function	Distillation Strategy	Node Degree 3		Node Degree 5		Node Degree 7	
		Accuracy	\pm Std. Dev.	Accuracy	\pm Std. Dev.	Accuracy	\pm Std. Dev.
CE	Holistic	61.96	0.41	66.61	1.77	68.29	1.77
	Pairwise	64.71	0.25	<u>68.99</u>	0.19	68.89	0.21
KL	Holistic	62.18	1.43	65.32	2.05	67.30	1.33
	Pairwise	<u>64.80</u>	0.32	69.06	0.08	68.86	0.16
TD	Holistic	64.43	0.28	68.31	0.87	71.36	0.55
	Pairwise	63.81	0.27	66.94	0.26	68.81	0.37
JS	Holistic	63.86	0.34	68.00	0.65	70.38	1.36
	Pairwise	62.84	0.16	65.28	0.24	66.65	0.23
SED	Holistic	64.05	0.33	67.74	0.30	<u>71.00</u>	0.64
	Pairwise	62.65	0.27	65.29	0.15	66.88	0.19
MSED	Holistic	66.82	0.28	67.88	0.17	68.02	0.25

Figure 5: Comparison of Average Accuracy ($\alpha = 0$: i.e. results for pure distillation), CIFAR-10. Average accuracy across 8 clients with node degree 5, 3 and 7, comparing the conventional sum of pairwise distillation (top row) and holistic (bottom row) approach. For each iteration, the average accuracy over all clients is reported, with error bars indicating the variance across clients. For reference, the result at iteration 0 shows the accuracy obtained using the first-head model trained with only supervised loss and no knowledge transfer. Points are slightly offset along the x-axis to improve readability and avoid overlap at identical iteration values.

Figure 6: Comparison of Average Accuracy ($\alpha = 0.5$: i.e. results using a combined loss with distillation), CIFAR-10. Average accuracy across 8 interconnected (node degree 3, 5 and 7), comparing the sum of pairwise distillation (top row) and holistic (bottom row) approach. For each iteration, the average accuracy over all clients is reported, with error bars indicating the variance across clients. For reference, the result at iteration 0 shows the accuracy obtained using the first-head model trained with only supervised loss and no knowledge transfer. Points are slightly offset along the x-axis to improve readability and avoid overlap at identical iteration values.

model (which was trained using ground-truth labels only), and also outperform the other divergence measures, which exhibit similar performance with respect to the first-head model.

In contrast, when adopting the holistic approach under the same connectivity setting (Figure 5d) for $\alpha = 0$, dissimilarity measures such as JS, TD, and SED provided slightly better performance compared to the first-head model in the first iteration. Most importantly, the holistic approach also significantly reduces the variance in this setting, indicating an overall advantage in using distillation from neighboring clients over a fully supervised approach relying solely on ground-truth labels. When combining the distillation loss with the supervised loss ($\alpha = 0.5$), as depicted in Figures 6a and 6d, we observe significant performance improvement with the holistic approach. This is particularly observed for dissimilarity measures such as TD, SED, and JS. Notably, JS consistently exhibits significantly low variance, which aligns with the results previously presented in Table 4. This improvement is evident both when compared to the first-head models and to the sum of pairwise distillation approach under the same conditions. In this setting, MSED's performance is initially observed to be less favorable compared to other divergence measures, which generally exhibit very similar performance among themselves. We found that MSED tends to improve its performance in later iterations than other dissimilarity measures, without significantly influencing the overall variance across iterations (see, e.g, Figure 6f).

It is important to note that MSED evaluates dissimilarity over a set of distributions, rather than through pairwise comparisons or comparisons with an averaged distribution. As a result, its behavior may differ substantially from the other tested functions. In particular, MSED is sensitive to the internal consistency of the set on which it is computed: a significant deviation by a single distribution can have a strong effect when the set is small, but this impact may be diluted when the set is large. In our case, MSED is used to assess the alignment between a client's prediction and those of its neighbors. However, this alignment is computed globally, based on the entropy of the entire set of predictions, and does not explicitly capture how different the client's prediction is from the neighbors. This means that if a client produces a distribution that significantly differs from those of its neighbors, while the neighbors are highly consistent among themselves, the MSED loss may remain low in earlier iterations and improve very late, especially when the node degree is high and thus global entropy is dominated by the majority.

As the node degree increases, we observe that in the setting where pairwise distillation is used, the CE and KL divergences generally outperform the other measures. However, this trend changes when the holistic approach is adopted: in that case, TD, JS, and SED tend to outperform CE and KL, particularly when the loss function combines both distillation and supervised losses ($\alpha = 0.5$).

As previously noted, the variance in accuracy across clients tends to decrease slightly for most of the divergence measures when the holistic approach is used. This suggests that holistic distillation promotes more consistent performance across clients.

Another interesting observation emerging in high node degree scenarios is the performance drop of certain divergence measures over iterations. This behavior is likely due to the increased sensitivity of the holistic approach to the temperature value, which smooths the averaged predictions from neighboring clients with respect to the prediction of a specific learning client. An inappropriate temperature value can, as explained in [16], result in a loss of critical information, contributing to this performance degradation. Therefore, developing an approach to dynamically regulate the temperature value during each client's learning phase could be a promising direction for future work.

4.2.3. Statistical Analysis of the effectiveness Holistic versus Pairwise Distillation

To quantitatively evaluate the performance differences between the holistic and pairwise distillation strategies and to complement the results obtained from a single seed in previous subsections, we conducted paired t-tests for each node degree using five different seeds. Running multiple seeds allows us to account for variability due to random initialization and better capture the robustness of each approach. The tests were performed on the best average accuracy achieved for each dissimilarity measure. Table 3 and Table 4 report the average accuracy across the five seeds along with the corresponding variance. Table 5 reports the results for two settings of the distillation parameter, $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 0.5$. The t-statistic reflects both the direction and magnitude of the difference, while the p-value indicates whether this difference is statistically significant.

For $\alpha = 0$, CE shows significant differences at all node degrees, with results favoring the pairwise approach, indicating that this measure consistently distinguishes between the two strategies. KL becomes significant only at moderate and higher node degrees, also favoring the pairwise approach, suggesting its sensitivity increases with connectivity. In contrast, TD is significant across all node degrees, while JS and SED become significant from $N = 5$ onward, with stronger effects at higher connectivity; for these measures, the results favor the holistic approach. Overall, these findings indicate that several measures consistently highlight differences between the two strategies: CE and KL emphasize the advantage of the pairwise approach, whereas TD, JS, and SED highlight the benefits of the holistic approach as node degree increases.

For $\alpha = 0.5$, the differences between the two approaches depend on both node degree and the divergence measure. At low connectivity ($N = 3$), all measures are significant, with CE and KL favoring the pairwise approach, while TD, JS, and SED favor the holistic one. This pattern persists at moderate connectivity ($N = 5$). At higher connectivity ($N = 7$), CE shows no significant difference and KL is only marginally significant, suggesting reduced sensitivity in denser networks. In contrast, TD, JS, and SED continue to reveal significant differences, generally in favor of the holistic approach. Taken together, these findings suggest that CE and KL are more informative in sparse settings, whereas TD, JS, and SED remain effective even as node degree increases.

Table 5: Paired t-test results for different dissimilarity measures, computed per node degree for each measure. The sign of the t-statistic indicates the favored strategy (positive for pairwise, negative for holistic).

function	$\alpha = 0$						$\alpha = 0.5$					
	Node Degree 3		Node Degree 5		Node Degree 7		Node Degree 3		Node Degree 5		Node Degree 7	
	t-stat	p-value	t-stat	p-value	t-stat	p-value	t-stat	p-value	t-stat	p-value	t-stat	p-value
CE	2.928	0.043	5.918	0.005	10.965	0.001	7.617	0.002	3.08	0.037	1.522	0.203
KL	2.242	0.089	4.221	0.014	9.647	0.001	4.387	0.012	3.979	0.017	2.753	0.052
TD	-3.167	0.034	-3.78	0.02	-20.754	0.001	-3.335	0.029	-2.93	0.043	-7.953	0.002
JS	-1.196	0.298	-15.09	0.001	-17.024	0.001	-6.391	0.004	-6.947	0.003	-6.432	0.004
SED	-1.537	0.2	-7.67	0.002	-35.577	0.001	-11.582	0.001	-14.264	0.001	-16.008	0.001

Overall, the results emphasize that the effectiveness of each distillation strategy is closely tied to the choice of dissimilarity measure. An interesting pattern emerges: the pairwise approach consistently benefits from asymmetric measures such as CE and KL, whereas the holistic approach gains more from symmetric measures like TD, JS, and SED. This suggests that the underlying structure of the knowledge transfer interacts with the properties of the measure. In pairwise distillation, where information flows directionally from a single teacher to a student, asymmetric measures may better capture the targeted guidance from one model to another. In contrast, holistic distillation aggregates information from multiple peers, making symmetric measures more appropriate as they emphasize mutual agreement and consensus across predictions. While a formal theoretical analysis is beyond the scope of this study, this pattern highlights a potentially fundamental relationship between the symmetry of a divergence measure and the collaborative versus directional nature of knowledge distillation, an insight that suggests further investigation in future work.

4.2.4. Trade-off Between Accuracy and Convergence Rate

In our experimental results, we compare the pairwise and holistic approaches to assess their trade-offs between accuracy and training efficiency. To further investigate which divergence measure provides the best compromise between convergence speed and final accuracy in this setting, Figure 7 summarizes the best accuracy achieved by each configuration along with the iteration at which it was reached.

Figures 7a and 7c show that the pairwise approach, despite achieving the highest accuracy with CE and KL divergences, fails to demonstrate an effective trade-off. This is evidenced by the consistent rightward shift of all associated points, indicating that convergence occurs significantly later. In other words, while accuracy may be high, it comes at the cost of slower convergence.

Considering the holistic approach with $\alpha = 0$, as shown in Figures 7b and 7d, JS demonstrates the most favorable trade-off across all node degrees. In contrast, MSED, CE, and KL exhibit slower convergence when compared to SED and TD. Similarly, for $\alpha = 0.5$, TD, SED, and JS consistently achieve the highest accuracy in networks with node degrees $N = 5$ and $N = 7$. Although MSED converges very late at higher node

Table 6: Best Iteration and Average Accuracy for the pairwise and holistic Distillation Strategies ($\alpha = 0.5$, node degree $N = 5$). The values in the parentheses represent the variance obtained for each dissimilarity measure. t^* is the best iteration. The values in bold represent the highest accuracy obtained within each node degree configuration, while underlined values indicate the second highest.

Function	Distillation Strategy	Iteration (t^*)	Average Accuracy at t^*
CE	Holistic	1	75.13 (± 5.69)
	Pairwise	10	76.04 (± 4.23)
KL	Holistic	1	75.22 (± 7.04)
	Pairwise	10	76.52 (± 3.61)
TD	Holistic	1	75.96 (± 7.53)
	Pairwise	10	75.27 (± 3.92)
JS	Holistic	1	76.03 (± 5.77)
	Pairwise	10	73.27 (± 5.06)
SED	Holistic	1	<u>76.78</u> (± 4.38)
	Pairwise	10	72.96 (± 5.81)
MSED	Holistic	10	77.34 (± 4.82)

degrees, and produces lower accuracy.

Overall, JS, TD and SED appear to offer the best trade-off between accuracy and convergence rate in the holistic setting, making them strong candidates as a divergence measure in distributed, distillation-based and holistic-based learning frameworks. In addition, the holistic approach stands out as the best overall strategy for scalable decentralized knowledge distillation, particularly in scenarios involving resource-constrained devices, due to its favorable convergence behavior.

4.3. Performance Evaluation using the Fashion-MNIST

In this section, we evaluate the studied distillation strategies using the Fashion-MNIST dataset to validate our findings from the in-depth CIFAR-10 study. In line with the trend observed in the first part of the experiment using CIFAR-10, Table 6 reveals that the holistic approach consistently achieves the best performance across all dissimilarity measures at the very first iteration, highlighting its superior convergence speed. In contrast, the pairwise approach shows gradual improvements over successive iterations.

(a) Pairwise approach with $\alpha = 0$

(b) Holistic approach with $\alpha = 0$

(c) Pairwise approach with $\alpha = 0.5$

(d) Holistic approach with $\alpha = 0.5$

Figure 7: Trade-off between accuracy and convergence rate, CIFAR-10. Each plot summarizes, for every divergence function and node degree, the iteration at which the best accuracy was reached and its corresponding value, using the holistic approach. Results are shown for $\alpha = 0$ (left) and $\alpha = 0.5$ (right). Points are slightly offset along the x-axis to improve readability and avoid overlap at identical iteration values.

(a) Pairwise approach with $\alpha = 0.5$

(b) Holistic approach with $\alpha = 0.5$

Figure 8: Comparison of Average Accuracy ($\alpha = 0.5$: i.e. results using a combined loss with distillation), Fashion-Mnist. Average accuracy across 8 interconnected (node degree 5), comparing the sum of pairwise distillation (left) and holistic (right) approach. For each iteration, the average accuracy over all clients is reported, with error bars indicating the variance across clients. For reference, the result at iteration 0 shows the accuracy obtained using the first-head model trained with only supervised loss and no knowledge transfer. Points are slightly offset along the x-axis to improve readability and avoid overlap at identical iteration values.

Figures 8a and 8b further illustrate the evolution of accuracy across iterations. In the pairwise setting, accuracy increases until approximately the sixth iteration before plateauing, indicating slower convergence. By comparison, the holistic strategy achieves peak performance immediately at the first iteration and maintains it with minimal variance, demonstrating both efficiency and effectiveness.

However, as seen in Figure 8b, MSED under the holistic setup continues to improve over iterations, deviating from the fast-convergence pattern exhibited by other measures. This behavior suggests that MSED may not be the most suitable option in decentralized holistic distillation scenarios, where early convergence is desirable.

5. Conclusions

This research provides key insights into the performance of KD-based decentralized learning, focusing on the impact of network topology, distillation strategies, and dissimilarity measures. We employed an iterative learning procedure that integrates models from direct neighbors and a client's previous state to evaluate different distillation strategies and dissimilarity measures.

Our empirical study reveals some key findings:

- *Network topology plays a critical role:* Higher node degrees consistently lead to improved average accuracy by promoting more effective knowledge propagation across the network.
- *Distillation strategy influences the effectiveness of dissimilarity measures:* The performance of a dissimilarity measure depends significantly on whether it is used in a pairwise or holistic distillation strategy.
- *Holistic distillation is generally more effective, but the choice of measure matters:* When used with symmetric distances such as TD, JS, and SED, holistic distillation yields faster convergence and reduced performance variance across heterogeneous clients. In contrast, asymmetric measures CE and KL divergence are better suited for pairwise strategies and may underperform in holistic settings.
- *Trade-offs between convergence rate and accuracy must be considered:* Holistic strategies with well-matched dissimilarity measures improve learning efficiency, key considerations for real-world deployment in resource-constrained or non-IID environments.

These findings offer practical guidance for designing KD-based decentralized learning systems. In particular, practitioners should carefully align the choice of dissimilarity measure with the chosen distillation strategy to optimize both accuracy and efficiency.

While our work focuses on an empirical comparison, we also recognize the theoretical relevance of certain divergence properties. Specifically, some of the functions used in our study

(namely, CE and KL) are Bregman divergences, whereas others, including JS, TD, and SED, are not. Although we do not explore the mathematical implications of this distinction, our results suggest that symmetric, non-Bregman divergences may offer advantages in holistic settings. Theoretical investigations on how these properties affect training dynamics and optimization behavior represent an important direction for future work.

Our future research will also focus on developing a dynamic stopping mechanism for the KD-based decentralized framework and assessing the communication costs on real-world devices, considering the heterogeneity of models and computing capabilities. Additionally, developing an approach to dynamically regulate the temperature value during each client's learning phase throughout iterations could be a promising direction for improving adaptation and performance across diverse training conditions. Furthermore, we plan to conduct a comparative study to investigate the performance of knowledge distillation in decentralized learning relative to a wide range of aggregation methods used in federated learning, to better understand their respective strengths and limitations across various scenarios.

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